

Local Government in South Africa

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Michelle R. Maziwisa and Jaap de Visser

Dullah Omar Institute, University of the Western Cape
with the support of SALGA - South African Local Government Association

Partners

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of

Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

University of the Western Cape: Michelle R.

Maziwisa, Jaap de Visser

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia

Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malfertheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Tobias Fischer/Unsplash

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Contents

1. The System of Local Government in South Africa	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in South Africa: An Introduction.....	7
2.2. ‘A Re Yeng’ Bus Rapid Transit Project: City of Tshwane	15
2.3. The Accreditation of Municipalities to Administer Housing Programmes.....	18
2.4. eThekweni Metropolitan Municipality: Expanded Public Services during the Covid-19 Emergency.	24
2.5. Procurement.....	29
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in South Africa: An Introduction	35
3.2. The Amalgamation of Municipalities in 2016	38
3.3. Metro Open Budget Survey.....	41
3.4. The Formalisation of Development Charges in South African Municipalities.....	45
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in South Africa: An Introduction.....	58
4.2. How Amalgamations Are Planned and Implemented	61
4.3. Local Boundary Changes and Public Participation	66
4.4. A District Coordinated Development Model	71
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in South Africa: An Introduction	76
5.2. Intergovernmental Cooperation in Fiscal and Financial Management: Bulk Resources for Municipal Services.....	82
5.3. Intergovernmental Relations through the Lenses of the Intergovernmental Division of Revenue ..	87
5.4. Intergovernmental Relations in Integrated Development Planning.....	92
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in South Africa: An Introduction.....	99
6.2. Participatory Budgeting.....	104
6.3. Municipal Budgeting and Planning during Covid-19.....	113
6.4. Transparency in Local Government Procurement during Covid-19.....	120

Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in South Africa: An Introduction

Melissa NS Ziswa, Dullah Omar Institute, University of the Western Cape

Section 40(1) of the South African Constitution entrenches the three levels of government, namely, national, provincial and local government. The local government as already discussed in South Africa's report section 2 (local responsibilities) is made up of category A, B and C municipalities. The type of categories is determined by the Municipal Demarcation Board based on the factors set out in Section 155 of the Constitution, and Section 2 of the Municipal Structures Act (MSA). Essentially, areas that comply with the criteria in Section 2 MSA are categorised as metropolitan municipalities and the rest of the country as district and local municipalities.

However, under apartheid, local government institutions were race-based. Racial segregation in South Africa ensured that there were community councils, advisory boards and local authorities appointed for black urban areas. These institutions lacked legitimacy, had little authority, were inadequately funded and often comprised of national government appointees. Black rural areas known as homelands had tribal authorities administering local government matters. Indian and coloured communities were governed by separate local government structures that were subordinate to the national and provincial governments. Lastly, fully-fledged local authorities governed exclusively white communities or areas. Apartheid aimed to limit the extent to which affluent white local municipalities would have to shoulder the financial burden for servicing the disadvantaged black communities. Therefore, when South Africa became a democracy there was dire need to integrate these fragmented local institutions. The amalgamation of municipalities was inevitable to achieve non-racial municipalities.

The main reasons behind the amalgamations between 1994 and 2000 were to integrate racially based local government institutions. However, after 2000, amalgamations were done mainly to ensure the financial viability of municipalities. The Municipal Demarcation Act provides the legal framework for the amalgamation of municipalities. This Act provides a firm guideline as to how amalgamations are planned and implemented. This section will elaborate more on how the amalgamation of municipalities is planned and implemented in the thematic practice below.

The three categories of local government (category A, B and C), are metropolitan municipalities (single-tier), district municipalities and local municipalities (multi-tier). South Africa has eight metropolitan municipalities. On one hand, metropolitan municipalities are stand-alone or single-tiered municipalities with a single council at the helm. The metropolitan council executes all the functions of local government for a city or conurbation. On the other hand, district municipalities comprise of two or more local municipalities. While some local

municipalities are secondary cities, or small towns, other local municipalities are rural. The local municipalities are represented on the district municipal council. District municipalities act as umbrella entities over local municipalities giving local municipalities support and assisting with coordination, planning and service delivery. This setup enables coordinated governance throughout the country.

In order to bring urban government closer to the people and improve service delivery, there are ward committees in all local municipalities and metropolitan municipalities. Section 72 (1) of the Structures Act establishes a legal framework for ward committees. The primary objective of ward committees is to enhance participatory democracy. Functions of the ward committee include making recommendations on matters affecting the ward to the ward councillor, through the ward councillor, to the metro or local council, the executive committee, the executive mayor or the relevant metropolitan subcouncil. Therefore, the ward committee serves as a formal communication channel between the ward community and the council and its political structures. Subcouncils in metropolitan areas also serve the purpose of bringing urban governance closer to the people. However, in terms of the Municipal Structures Act, only certain types of metropolitan municipalities may establish metropolitan subcouncils. To date only Cape Town Metropolitan Municipality has a subcouncil. In order to establish the subcouncil, the municipality must adopt a by-law determining the number of subcouncils that are to be established. In addition to that, the municipality must designate a cluster of adjoining wards to the subcouncil. Among the powers and functions of subcouncils is the ability to make recommendations to the metro council on matters affecting its area. Such functions of subcouncils bring urban government closer to the people thus facilitating improvement in services.

The legal framework for horizontal inter-municipal cooperation is the Intergovernmental Relations Framework Act (IGRFA), which provides for vertical and horizontal intergovernmental relations (report section 4). This Act is a manifestation of Chapter 3 of the Constitution, which discusses co-operative government. Section 16 of the IGRFA provides for the Premier's Intergovernmental Forum (PIF) to promote and facilitate intergovernmental relations between the province and local governments in the province. In Section 24, the IGRFA also provides for district intergovernmental forums, which facilitate intergovernmental relations between district municipalities and local municipalities within the district. The IGRFA also provides for the establishment of inter-municipality forums in Section 28. These platforms serve as a consultative forum for participating municipalities to discuss and consult each other on matters of mutual interest.

In the South African case, several factors can facilitate or impede effective inter-municipal cooperation. The Gauteng City Region is an example of the challenge in managing large interconnected urbanised spaces that are governed by multiple local government structures. For instance, spatial and institutional fragmentation hampers development in the Gauteng City Region. Government institutions fail to align their programmes and projects, particularly with respect to infrastructure development. In certain instances, subsidies are transferred from the

national government to provincial governments. The latter in turn transfer those subsidies to municipalities. Delays and bureaucracy often hinder this, particularly if the provincial political party is different from the local government municipalities. This is also precipitated by the lack of shared vision among the municipalities. Previously when one political party governed both provinces and municipalities, it was possible for intergovernmental disputes to be resolved informally at the political party headquarters. Now with different political parties at the helm, this is no longer possible. On the other hand, legislation such as the National Land Transport Act 5 of 2009 facilitates inter-municipal cooperation. The act allows for the creation of a special purpose authority that brings together national, provincial and municipal transport functions into one jointly controlled entity.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996

Municipal Structures Act 117 of 1998

National Land Transport Act 5 of 2009

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

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